

METHODOLOGY OF USING PROJECT TECHNOLOGY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the methodology for using project technology in foreign language education. Furthermore, it discusses successful methodologies and their significance in the educational process.

Keywords: foreign language, methodology, project technology, assignment.

In the modern era of globalization, the demand for learning foreign languages requires not only memorizing grammatical rules but also developing the ability to use the language freely in real communication processes. Within the framework of reforms carried out in the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, developing the communicative competencies of students has been designated as a priority task. In this regard, it is highly relevant to move away from traditional teaching methods and implement innovative and person-centered technologies, specifically project technology, into the classroom process.

"Phrasebook." The goal of the project is for students to create an educational phrasebook containing expressions they would need during a stay in Cambridge. The phrasebook is divided into several sections: asking for directions; communicating with a host family; conversations about food; expressing gratitude, and so on. The number of sections and their content depend on the students' language proficiency level. The particular value of this assignment lies in its practical orientation: students who complete the project can later pass this phrasebook on to newly arrived students.

"Poster Projects." According to the project author, such assignments are very convenient for concluding a course. The project is implemented in several stages:

Dividing students into groups.

Selecting a topic that is interesting to them and directly related to their studies or stay in England.

Independent work by students to prepare materials related to the project (photographs, drawings, etc.).

Creating a poster consisting of information and visual materials.

Conducting an open lesson where students present their posters to one another.

The author emphasizes that the assignment for this project can be given as soon as students begin their studies. In this way, the project encourages them to constantly collect information to complete the task – promoting independent

work and motivating them to apply the language being studied outside the classroom.

"Student Guidebook." Another useful project is the creation of a guidebook for the city and the educational institution where the students are studying. This guidebook, like the phrasebook described above, can subsequently be used in teaching future groups of students. The guidebook may include the following sections:

Where to go?

Where to eat?

Best places to shop.

Visiting guests.

Introduction to the school.

Situations to avoid.

Similar to the previous project, this task can be performed by students throughout the entire course.

The assignments we have presented fully meet the requirements for using the project method in foreign language teaching: they allow students to demonstrate their creative abilities and involve presenting the results of their work using the language being studied. It should also be noted that, following the lead of foreign textbooks, this curriculum proposes incorporating project work into the educational process from the very beginning stages of teaching.

However, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how the project method functions in foreign language teaching, it is also necessary to analyze examples of projects that do not fully align with their designation.

The study guide titled "Timesaver. Project work," as the name suggests, is designed to lighten the teacher's workload through pre-developed projects. The projects in this book are divided into three groups according to language proficiency levels: beginner, elementary, and threshold (intermediate). The introduction of the book provides fundamental recommendations typical of the project methodology for working with projects. However, in our opinion, not all of the proposed activities can be strictly classified as "authentic" projects. Let us analyze one of the project assignments for the beginner level.

This project is conducted during the lesson process, and its objective is to learn and reinforce new vocabulary related to the theme "Classroom Objects" (pencil, pen, dictionary, scissors, ruler, etc.). Work on the project is carried out step-by-step:

Students take out their existing writing and stationery supplies and recall or learn their names in English.

Each student receives a worksheet aimed at matching words with the corresponding pictures. This task can be performed in pairs. The teacher checks the correct completion of the task and student pronunciation, demonstrates the use of questions such as “Do you have...?” and “Can I have...?” and monitors the correct use of articles during this process.

Students in each pair receive different versions of the same picture. These pictures contain some items necessary for the classroom while others are missing. On the right side of the picture, a prompt is provided—images of the items that should be in the picture and question forms. Working in pairs, students ask questions based on the pictures. Their task is to identify four items that are missing from both pictures once the questioning is complete.

In the next stage, the teacher attaches pre-prepared phrases to the board (e.g., “I’m sorry, I don’t understand,” “Could you repeat that, please?”, “How do you spell...?” etc.). A symbol or picture representing its meaning is drawn next to each phrase. Then, the teacher removes the phrases one by one, leaving only the pictures, and checks whether the students remember the sentences. At the end of the session, the phrases are returned to their places, and students copy them into their notebooks.

In the following session, the pictures and symbols are drawn on the board again to review the previously learned phrases.

Although this project – the first one in the manual – is designated as preparation for students' subsequent project activities, we cannot agree with the notion that the aforementioned set of tasks can be called a "project." Firstly, none of the tasks allow students the opportunity to choose at least the format of the work, which is one of the essential characteristics of project-based activity. Secondly, there is no final result presented in the form of a tangible product. The outcome of this sequence of tasks is merely the learning of certain phrases, which students will subsequently use during lessons.

In our view, the "project-like" nature of this assignment lies only in the fact that students (if they were not previously familiar) become acquainted with more interactive forms of work and thereby realize that a language can be learned through ways other than just performing tedious grammatical exercises. However, we believe that in the modern methodology of foreign language teaching, such a scenario has already become a rare occurrence. It should be noted that the majority of assignments in this study guide are indeed true projects and

meet all the requirements of this method; however, to provide a complete picture, we deemed it necessary to cite examples of tasks that are called "projects" in name only, but not in essence.

Our work also analyzes a project design created by educators teaching English as a foreign language for Kwansei Gakuin University in Japan. Unlike the previously described study guides intended for any student learning English, this design was created for a specific target audience, taking into account particular student characteristics. We believe it is necessary to present it to gain a more thorough understanding of the role of the project method in international foreign language teaching methodology.

It is particularly noteworthy that the authors prepared a specialized design for a seven-day intensive English course. This course is conducted in two stages: 2 days at the beginning of August and 5 days at the beginning of September. The second part of the course is organized at the university's retreat house, and during this period, students are constantly accompanied by a foreign language teacher. The course encompasses a total of 50 academic hours, 22 of which involve students working in groups of 8–10 under the guidance of a native-speaking teacher. In the interval between the two parts of the course (the August and September stages), students carry out independent work on the project. According to the authors of this design, in such an educational environment, project work serves as a vital stimulating and motivational factor, and also helps to diversify the forms of work offered to students. This is especially important in the conditions of a short-term and high-intensity educational process.

The "Wikipedia" Project. Assignment: To create a page in English about the university's retreat house on Wikipedia – the free internet encyclopedia – and to prepare a 15-minute professional PowerPoint presentation on the project.

The first stage of the work involves familiarizing students with other pages on Wikipedia and generating project ideas using the "brainstorming" method (determining what the Wikipedia page should look like). The most interesting ideas proposed by students are selected, and versions approved by the majority are adopted. This stage is carried out in August. Following this, students search for suitable citations, photographs, and other materials for the retreat house's Wikipedia page and exchange them with other course participants via a specialized online platform.

During the second part of the course, students create the page on Wikipedia and prepare a presentation dedicated to it.

The project authors note that certain difficulties arose during the implementation process. For instance, students struggled to find pages on relevant topics in English; consequently, teachers were forced to rely on the native language more than originally planned. Another issue was related to publishing the page on the Wikipedia site, as the platform maintains specific rules for publishing articles. As a result, the page created by the students was edited by Wikipedia staff.

The practical orientation of this project and its execution within a phenomenon well-known to students – Wikipedia – served to further motivate learners and allowed for the organization of their independent work during the summer break. However, it should also be noted that the teachers who developed the project were not sufficiently prepared for its execution, as they did not anticipate the difficulties that would arise during the information search process. In our opinion, teachers' preparation for implementing projects they have designed, especially on such specific topics, must be more meticulous. That is, before assigning a task to students, they should walk the student's path themselves, attempt to create a similar project, and ensure that the proposed assignment is truly feasible.

The examples of successful and less successful projects presented above are, in our view, essential for determining the most optimal strategy for using the project method in the classroom. The lack of a precise definition for the term “project” and its popularity provide extensive material for research on one hand, while on the other, they urge caution when using ready-made projects found in foreign language textbooks and methodological recommendations. Undoubtedly, projects can be applied in foreign language teaching from the very first lessons. Furthermore, a teacher can develop projects that are not only interesting to students as an unconventional form of creative work but also allow for the creation of a product that can be used in practice.

At the same time, not every creative or group activity can be termed project-based work. Teachers must keep in mind that the primary goal of any interactive and creative activity in foreign language teaching is the formation of communicative competence.

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